

**EXPECTATIONS OF RESPONDENTS FROM THE TAMIL
NADU STATE TRANSPORT CORPORATION – A STUDY IN
TIRUNELVELI DIVISION**

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Cite This Article: K. Varghese & Dr. S. Maria John, "Expectations of Respondents from the Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporation – A Study in Tirunelveli Division" *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities*, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 71-75, 2018.

Abstract:

This study mainly focuses on finding out the expectations of Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporation labourers on the five chosen welfare schemes and their attitude towards the implementation of those welfare schemes. Job on compassionate grounds, Quota in admissions, Housing facilities, Freebus pass and Training to dependants were the five study variables. A sample of 290 respondents, including drivers, conductors and technical staff by applying stratified random technique, were selected and the data were collected through a well-designed and structured interview schedule. Tirunelveli Division, that comprises Kanyakumari, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi districts, was the study field. 'F' test was applied to get the statistical results. The study reveals that the employees at different levels express that the welfare schemes are not fully implemented and expect that they should be implemented to alleviate their sufferings and to create a better work environment.

Key Words: Compassionate Grounds, Quota in Admissions, Housing Facilities, Bus Pass & Training

Introduction:

Transportation plays a very dominant role in the service sectors because people cannot perform their daily duties without moving from one place to another place. The transport sector has two operators: (i) the public undertakings run by the government and (ii) the private. These both sectors are servicing the public with quality. The quality of the transport system is a prime indicator of economic prosperity and development of a State. A good road network is a prerequisite for the success of all economic activities. The transport department is committed to provide high quality service to the citizens through adequate enforcement of statutory and non-statutory regulations coupled with modernisation and computerisation. The major objectives of the transport department are: (i) To provide efficient delivery of all its services to the citizens; (ii) Maximising revenue to the Government by ensuring that all taxes and fees on vehicles are collected without any leakage; (iii) Promoting road safety and providing relief to the victims of road accidents and (iv) controlling vehicular pollution.

Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporation (TNSTC) performs the work of transportation in Tamil Nadu. In TNSTC, many types of employees are working. It provides numerous labour welfare measures with the objective of developing the standard of living of the employees. Though they avail all welfare measures, they expect more from the Department, as they are not satisfied with those welfare measures. So this study was undertaken. The main objective is to study some of the expectations of the respondents from the TNSTC. The study area selected for the study is Tirunelveli Division which covers Kanyakumari, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi districts. A sample of 120 drivers, 130 conductors and 40 technical staffs were selected as respondent by applying stratified random technique. Data were collected from these 290 respondents through a well designed and structured interview schedule. The collected data were subjected to statistical analysis. The variables selected were: (i) Job on compassionate grounds, (ii) Quota in admissions, (iii) Housing facilities, (iv) Freebus pass and (v) Training to dependants.

The expectations of respondents differ from employee to employee. It was decided to find out the exact relationship among the three category of respondents namely (i) Drivers, (ii) Conductors and (iii) Technical Staff. Statistical applications like mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation were found out from the data collected using Likert fivepoint scale technique.

The hypotheses on the variables were framed to determine whether there existed a significant difference between the different groups and within the groups of the three categories of respondents. 'F' test was applied and the results were interpreted.

1. Job on Compassionate Grounds and Expectation:

A job provides life and bread to the dependants of an employee. When an employee is in service, he will be getting a regular income with all perks, by which his family will be living happily. On the other hand, when one is put to risk (death), many a time, his family is put to hardships. So the employees expect job on compassionate grounds. In order to ascertain the significant relationship between job on compassionate ground and expectation, data relating to the opinion of the respondents on the statement job on compassionate ground were collected by Likert five point scaling technique and analysed. The results of analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Job on Compassionate Ground and Expectation Analysis

S.No.	Group	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	Coefficient Variation
1	Drivers	120	3.961	0.589	0.0361	14.87
2	Conductors	130	3.854	0.493	0.0490	12.79
3	Technical Staff	40	4.001	0.485	0.262	12.12
	Total	290	3.939	0.522	0.382	13.25

Source: Computed data

Table1 reveals that there are minor differences in the means of the three categories of respondents regarding the expectation on job on compassionate ground. The analysis shows that the technical staff category respondents have the maximum mean score of 4.001, while the conductor category respondents have a low mean score of 3.854. But the standard deviation was more in driver category respondents and least in technical staff category. By comparing the co-efficient of variation, it is inferred that it is less in technical staff category respondents, for they get jobs easily than the other two categories of respondents. Higher variation is identified in drivers' category for non availability of job on compassionate grounds.

Relationship Testing:

In order to investigate the existence of relation between different categories namely drivers, conductors and technical staff on expectation towards job on compassionate grounds, a one-way ANOVA was used to determine whether there existed a significant difference between groups and within groups of the three major categories of TNSTC employees. The results of one-way ANOVA is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: ANOVA of Expectation

S.No.	Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F Ratio	Significance
1	Between Groups	3	1.611	0.537	14.962	.000
2	Within Groups	286	146.851	0.513		
	Total	289	148.462			

Source: Computed data

It is evident from Table2 that the calculated value of F ratio (14.962) is greater than the critical value of F distribution with three and 289 degrees of freedom, whereas it is 2.65 in the 'F' table. So the null hypothesis that there is no significant of relationship between job on compassionate grounds and expectation of the respondents is rejected. Hence it is concluded that there is significant relationship between the variable and expectation of the respondents.

2. Quota in Admissions:

Education to wards of the employees is a necessity now-a-days. Many wards are going for higher education in order to stabilize and strengthen their future. All are not meritorious. Hence when quota in admissions to courses like M.B.B.S., B.E., B.L., Agriculture and the like are provided, it may be a helping hand to the generations. So the employees expect a quota.

In order to ascertain the significant relationship between quota in admissions and expectation, data relating to the opinion of the respondents on the statement quota in admissions were collected using Likert five points scaling technique and analysed. The results of analysis are presented in Table.3.

Table 3: Quota in Admissions and Expectation Analysis

S.No.	Group	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	Coefficient Variation
1	Drivers	120	2.998	1.1110	0.0844	37.25
2	Conductors	130	3.237	0.7285	0.0554	22.5
3	Technical Staff	40	3.429	0.9376	0.251	27.35
	Total	290	3.125	0.9462	0.0499	30.22

Source: Computed data

Table3 reveals that there are minor differences in the means of the three categories of respondents regarding expectation on quota in admissions. The analysis shows that the technical staff category respondents have the maximum mean score of 3.429 while the driver category respondents have a low mean score of 2.998. Accordingly the standard deviation was more in drivers category respondents and least in conductor category. By comparing the co-efficient of variation, it is inferred that it is less in conductor category respondents, for they are familiar with the quota system than the other two categories of respondents. Higher variation is identified in driver category for non exposure.

Relationship Testing:

In order to investigate the existence of relation between different categories namely drivers, conductors and technical staff on expectation to the wards quota in admissions a one-way ANOVA was used to determine whether there existed a significant difference between groups and within groups of the three major categories of TNSTC employees. The results of one way ANOVA is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: ANOVA of Expectation

S.No.	Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F Ratio	Significance
1	Between Groups	3	1.763	.588	6.765	.000
2	Within Groups	286	258.366	0.894		
	Total	289	259.129			

Source: Computed data

It is evident from Table 4 that the calculated value of F ratio (6.765) is greater than the critical value of F distribution with three and 286 degrees of freedom, whereas it is 2.65 in the 'F' table. So the null hypothesis that there is no significant of relationship between quota in admissions and expectation of the respondents is rejected. Hence it is concluded that there is significant relationship between the variable and expectation of the respondents.

3. Housing Facilities:

In order to live, food is the basic necessity followed by clothing. But shelter is equally important as that of the previous two requisites. If one wants to live, he needs accommodation, for which houses are needed. The TADHDCO is providing house to a category of Indian citizens. Housing facility can also be provided to transport workers. This is another expectation of the TNSTC employees. In order to ascertain the significant relationship between housing facilities and expectation, data relating to the opinion of the respondents on the statement housing facilities were collected by Likert five points scaling technique and analysed. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Housing Facilities and Expectation Analysis

S.No.	Group	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	Coefficient Variation
1	Drivers	120	2.486	0.7361	0.0560	29.56
2	Conductors	130	2.942	0.2341	0.0178	7.96
3	Technical Staff	40	3.714	0.4688	0.1253	12.64
	Total	290	2.753	0.6177	0.0326	22.47

Source: Computed data

Table 5 reveals that there are minor differences in the means of the three category of respondents regarding expectation on housing facilities. The analysis shows that the technical staff category respondents have the maximum mean score of 3.714 while the driver category respondents have a low mean score of 2.486. Accordingly the standard deviation was more in driver category respondents and least in conductor category. By comparing the co-efficient of variation, it is inferred that it is less in conductor category respondents than the other two categories of respondents. Higher variation is identified in driver category of respondents.

Relationship Testing:

In order to investigate the existence of relation between different categories namely drivers, conductors and technical staff on expectation towards housing facilities a one way ANOVA was used to determine where there existed a significant difference between groups and with in groups of the three major categories of TNSTC employees. The results of one-way ANOVA is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: ANOVA of Expectation

S.No.	Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F Ratio	Significance
1	Between Groups	3	1.562	0.5206	12.615	.000
2	Within Groups	286	48.962	0.1712		
	Total	289	50.524			

Source: Computed data

It is evident from Table 6 that the calculated value of F ratio (12.615) is greater than the critical value of F distribution with three and 286 degrees of freedom, whereas it is 2.65 in the 'F' table. So the null hypothesis that there is significant relationship between housing facilities and expectation of the respondents is rejected. Hence it is concluded that there is significant relationship between the variable and expectation of the respondents.

4. Free Bus Pass:

When one works as an employee in the TNSTC either as an administrative/technical staff, driver or conductor, he is free to travel in buses within the jurisdiction of the corporation. But when he retires, he will not be provided with the free pass which he availed while he was in service. But what is needed is free pass to not only to the retired person but also to his dependants.

In order to ascertain the significant relationship between free bus pass and expectation, data relating to the opinion of the respondents on free bus pass collected by Likert five points scaling technique and analysed. The results of analysis are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Free Bus Pass Expectation Analysis

S.No.	Group	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	Coefficient Variation
1	Drivers	120	2.850	0.571	0.0434	20.04
2	Conductors	130	4.098	0.880	0.0670	21.46
3	Technical Staff	40	4.071	0.829	0.2215	20.37
	Total	290	3.497	0.970	0.0511	27.71

Source: Computed data

Table 7 reveals that there are minor differences in the means of the three category of respondents regarding expectation free bus pass. The analysis shows that the conductor category respondents have the maximum mean score of 4.098 while the driver category respondents have a low mean score of 2.850. Accordingly the standard deviation was more in conductor category respondents and least in driver category. By comparing the co-efficient of variation, it is inferred that it is less in driver category respondents, for they are provided with free bus pass than the other two categories of respondents. Higher variation is identified in conductor category for non-sparing of time.

Relationship Testing:

In order to investigate the existence of relation between different categories namely drivers, conductors and technical staff on expectation towards free bus pass a one-way ANOVA was used to determine where there existed a significant difference between groups and with in groups of the three categories of TNSSTC employees. The results of one way ANOVA is presented in Table 8.

Table 8: ANOVA of Expectation

S.No.	Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F Ratio	Significance
1	Between Groups	3	0.992	0.330	7.892	.000
2	Within Groups	286	210.150	0.7347		
	Total	289	211.142			

Source: Computed data

It is evident from Table 8 that the calculated value of F ratio (7.892) is greater than the critical value of F distribution with three and 286 degrees of freedom, whereas it is 2.65 in the 'F' table. So the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between free bus pass and expectation of the respondents is rejected. Hence it is concluded that there is significant relationship between the variable and expectation of the respondents.

5. Training to Dependants:

Most of the dependants of the employees of TNSSTC are not going for any job even though they are either graduates or with atleast some qualification. They expect conduct of training programmes on entrepreneurship which may boost their level of income and standard of living. So they need Entrepreneurship Development Programme (EDP) to some level.

In order to ascertain the significant relationship between training to dependants and expectation, data relating to the opinion of the respondents on the statement increased resource sharing ability were collected by Likert five points scaling technique and analysed. The results of analysis are presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Training to Dependants and Expectation Analysis

S.No.	Group	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	Coefficient Variation
1	Drivers	120	2.642	0.813	0.0618	30.80
2	Conductors	130	3.064	0.666	0.0507	21.76
3	Technical Staff	40	3.286	0.825	0.221	25.23
	Total	290	2.870	0.777	0.0496	27.07

Source: Computed data

Table 9 reveals that there are minor differences in the means of the three categories of respondents regarding expectation on training to dependants. The analysis shows that the technical staff category respondents have the maximum mean score of 3.286 while the driver category respondents have a low mean score of 2.642. Accordingly the standard deviation was more in technical staff category respondents and least in conductor category. By comparing the co-efficient of variation, it is inferred that it is less in conductor category respondents than the other two categories of respondents. Higher variation is identified in driver category.

Relationship Testing:

In order to investigate the existence of relation between different categories namely drivers, conductors and technical staff on expectation towards increased resource sharing ability a one-way ANOVA was used to determine whether there existed a significant difference between groups and with in groups of the three major categories of TNSSTC employees. The results of one way ANOVA is presented in Table10.

Table 10: ANOVA of Expectation

S.No.	Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F Ratio	Significance
1	Between Groups	3	1.501	0.500	19.688	.000
2	Within Groups	286	294.367	1.029		
	Total	289	295.868			

Source: Computed data

It is evident from Table 10 that the calculated value of F ratio (19.688) is greater than the critical value of F distribution with three and 286 degrees of freedom, whereas it is 2.65 in the 'F' table. So the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between training to dependants and expectation of the respondents is rejected. Hence it is concluded that there is significant relationship between the variable and expectation of the respondents.

Findings and Suggestions:

It has been observed from the study that, of the five variables identified and analysed, it was found that there has been a significant influence of the variables and expectation in among all the five factors. On the basis of the findings of the study, the following suggestions are recommended:

- ✓ Job on compassionate ground should be given with immediate effect so that the family of the deceased employees may not be further affected. Quota in admissions, if provided, may lift up the families of TNSTC employees.
- ✓ Housing loan may be provided at a very low interest rate.
- ✓ Free bus pass to all the dependants, if given, will result in promoting the level of sincerity in their works.
- ✓ Living quarters to all the workers of TNSTC may be provided.
- ✓ Training to the dependents through CEDs (Centre for Entrepreneurial Development) may be given at the State and District level.
- ✓ When these suggestions are put to practice, the standard of living of the TNSTC community will improve.
- ✓ Many welfare measures are available to the workers but still some of them remain at the paper level only. Implementing them will create and develop a very good industrial relations in the organisation.

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